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Efficiency and Comfort in IoT-Controlled HVAC: Exploring Flexible Setpoints for Infrequent Office Occupancy

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Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive study investigating the implementation of flexible heating and cooling setpoints in infrequently occupied spaces, focusing on meeting and training rooms. The research showcases the practical application in an office building located in Glasgow, featuring six meeting rooms and one training room. The study utilizes a sophisticated digital-twin model, calibrated on an hourly basis for electricity, heating energy consumption and Indoor Air Quality (IAQ) measures. Through simulation analysis, the model reveals significant energy savings and improved comfort levels within these spaces.

Furthermore, the paper provides evidence derived from the real-world implementation of the proposed approach in the same office building. This implementation leverages a combination of motion sensors and smart Thermostatic Radiator Valves (TRVs). The research findings indicate that the application of flexible heating and cooling setpoints in the office building can open the door to savings by avoiding unnecessary heating or cooling. However, the savings are solely dependent on several factors, including the number of spaces suitable for this technique, the heat loss characteristics of these spaces, and their occupancy patterns.

In addition to energy savings, the study investigates potential compromises in occupant comfort, particularly concerning the time required for the system to reach the desired setpoint when occupants first enter the space in the morning, particularly in winter. The paper offers innovative solutions to address these comfort challenges, ensuring that energy-efficient practices do not affect the well-being of building occupants.

Keywords IoT in HVAC, Occupancy triggered heating, Physics-based Digital Twins, Energy Model Calibration

1.0 Introduction

The study delves into the intricate challenge of optimizing heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems in infrequently occupied spaces, specifically targeting meeting and training rooms. Traditionally governed by rigid schedules, HVAC operations face scrutiny for their effectiveness, especially in spaces with sporadic occupancy patterns. This paper explores the implementation of adaptable heating

and cooling setpoints, leveraging IoT technology. The parameters under scrutiny include electricity use, heating energy, and indoor air quality. The research unfolds in a Glasgow office building, extending its scope to the World Trading Centre (WTC) in Grenoble, France, providing a comprehensive analysis of energy efficiency and comfort implications. Furthermore, the study delves into the challenges associated with such implementations, addressing the complexities and considerations involved in balancing energy efficiency and occupant comfort.

2.0 Background and Motivation

In commercial and educational buildings, empty meeting and lecturing rooms are frequently heated without apparent justification, particularly in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic and the widespread adoption of hybrid working models by many companies and educational institutions.

Peper & Feist (1) emphasize that occupants' behaviour has a significant impact on actual energy consumption, accounting for approximately $\pm 50\%$. Consequently, the influence of occupants' behaviour should not be overlooked.

Upon analysing office buildings, it has been observed that rooms are not consistently fully occupied during daytime, and certain rooms are routinely unoccupied (3). Monitoring studies have indicated that the average occupancy in offices is approximately 60% (4). For example, on days characterized by reduced activity when individuals opt for remote work, there are fewer in-person meetings and lectures, resulting in these rooms remaining unoccupied for the majority of the day. If these spaces are heated uniformly alongside the rest of the building, it can result in overlooking easily preventable heat losses.

As occupancy behaviours put real research challenges in regards to building energy policy making particularly when trying to define or estimate (5), one proposed solution is to integrate occupancy monitoring with the heating/cooling system in these specific spaces, mitigating unnecessary heat losses.

3.0 Focus on Meeting and Training Rooms

Meeting and training rooms present certain challenges, notably their infrequent occupancy throughout the entire week. Typically, these spaces adhere to regular schedules aligned with planned trainings or meetings. The absence of intelligent heating systems hampers the efficient determination of whether to heat the space or not. Moreover, the task of isolating the space system from the building-level system introduces additional challenges, necessitating investments in IoT infrastructure.

Traditionally, these areas have been subject to the same heating and cooling practices as regularly occupied spaces, despite their distinct patterns of use. A reevaluation of heating and cooling strategies in these spaces is crucial to align practices with the actual demand, optimizing energy efficiency, and ensuring a more sustainable and responsive utilization of resources.

Digital Modelling in Glasgow Office Building:

An energy model was crafted for the Helix building situated in the western part of Glasgow, featuring two floors dedicated to offices, each occupied by separate companies. The study specifically zooms in on the ground floor, known for its predominant heating demands. Employing the IES-VE software, the energy model

underwent calibration against real-time measurements on an hourly basis to align with the prescribed thresholds outlined in the ASHRAE Guidelines (6).

This calibration process extended to both electricity and heating energy, the latter sourced from a biomass boiler housed separately outside the main building. In refining the precision of the calibrated energy model, calibration efforts were extended to Indoor Environmental Measures, shaping what is referred to as a Physics-based Digital Twin (PbDT). For heightened accuracy, the model also integrated operational profiles derived from IoT data for equipment, lighting, and occupancy levels in each simulation timestep. Leveraging information from CO₂ concentration levels and motion detection devices to more capture the actual performance dynamics of the building. In addition to that windows were operated in the model in accordance with actual behaviours of the occupants using the data provided by the window opening sensors.

Figures 1 and 2 show the energy model and the actual building.

Figure 1 – Helix Building Model in IES-VE

Figure 1 – Helix Building picture (taken 2022)

Figures 3 and 4 show a month plot of the simulation Vs actual measurements from IoT, plotted using IES-iSCAN Data Analysis Tool (11).

Figure 3 – CO2 levels Calibrated model (blue) and actual readings (Orange)

Figure 4 – Indoor temperature Calibrated model (blue) and actual readings (Green)

4.0 Variable Setpoints for Variable Occupancy Patterns

There is a debate whether or not heat empty spaces can save energy in building level in the long term. However, the fact that the heat losses will increase as a result of a higher temperature differences alone can prove that this is just a myth. In commercial and educational buildings, we often see meeting and lecturing rooms being heated with no obvious reason specially post covid-19 pandemic and the adoption of hybrid working by many companies and education facilities. For instance, in quieter days where people prefer working from home, there are less meetings and lectures held in person, and therefore such rooms can be empty for most the day. If heated the same way as the rest of the building this can lead to easily avoided heat losses to be missed.

The Physics-based Digital Twin empowers the evaluation of occupancy-triggered radiator scenarios by incorporating data from motion sensors into simulations. The specific scenario unfolds as follows:

- Radiators in meeting rooms feature adaptable setpoints determined by the heating schedule and occupancy status, informed by motion sensor data.
- The setpoint during non-working hours is set to 15°C.
- Within working hours, two distinct setpoints exist. The default is 17°C, and only upon motion detection should the setpoint shift to 19°C.
- The setpoint reverts to the default (17°C) when no motion is detected in the room for 5 minutes.

With these parameters applied to our digital twin, we can accurately gauge the outcomes and estimate potential savings from such implementations. Figure 3 illustrates the simulated temperature in one of the meeting rooms at the Helix building, incorporating both variable setpoints and the carefully positioned motion sensor on the room's side wall to detect occupant presence. Figure 5 shows an example of the IESV-VE simulated air temperature using flexible setpoint, plotted using IES-iSCAN Data Analysis Tool (11).

Figure 2 – Simulated indoor temperature (Green) with flexible setpoint (Orange) based on a motion sensor (Blue).

When the motion sensor detects occupancy, the target temperature changes, activating the heating system in our simulation. Using real measured data is essential to get accurate results, ensuring that our simulation reflects how the pattern on which the building occupants behave and how that affects the heating system.

The model not only made it possible for the scenario to be tested before total implementation, but also, allowed for the evaluation of things like comfort index. As, the TRVs will be changed to smart ones, the setpoint is no longer adjustable by the occupants, this means that the valve will not be forgotten at 28°C setpoint for the next occupant to feel uncomfortably hot. The model showed an improved Predictive Mean Vote (PMV) values when using remotely controlled TRVs with variable setpoints compared to the DT adjusted baseline simulation which was done according to the International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol IPMVP (7).

Figures 6 and 7 give an example for the variation in PMV during occupied hours (when motion is detected) for both the DT baseline and the DT with smart TRVs.

Figure 3 – Example of the PMV values from simulation for number of hours the room was occupied before implementing flexible setpoints (Blue) and after (Orange)

Figure 4 – The variation and mean in PMV values from simulation for number of hours the room was occupied before implementing flexible setpoints (Orange) and after (Grey)

The presented findings indicate that optimizing PMV values in the specific room can be achieved by redistributing votes from the 0.5-1 band to the -0.5-0 band during simulated occupied hours. Despite this adjustment, it is noteworthy that more than 30% of the total hours originally falling within the 0-0.5 band would be shifted to the -0.5-0 range.

This strategic redistribution implies a significant improvement in occupant comfort, as there would be no instances of uncomfortably high temperatures, given that the radiators will not be set to high levels accessible for adjustment by the occupant. Nevertheless, this enhancement comes at the cost of a trade-off, as a portion of the hours would now fall within the -0.5-0 band, resulting in a slightly cooler environment.

This compromise is attributed to the time required for the room to reach the desired temperature after occupancy, typically ranging from 10 to 15 minutes for the Helix radiator system. This temporary sensation of chill as the room transitions to the desired temperature is seen as a worthwhile trade-off in the larger context of improving energy efficiency while maintaining an acceptable level of comfort for the occupants.

5.0 Real-world Implementation in Glasgow Office Building

The Energy Conservation Measure (ECM) was implemented in November 2022, and to validate its impact, we conducted a simulation a pracademic year (COVID-19). Utilizing 2019 weather data and IoT-driven occupancy profiles for all meeting rooms, the simulation revealed a measured energy use for heating on the ground floor of 5.23 MWh.

Comparing this to the actual heating energy consumed in December 2019 (5.87 MWh), the simulation using the calibrated model for the same year closely matched at 5.8 MWh, demonstrating the model's accuracy.

Subsequently, using the same model with a 2022 weather file yielded a simulated energy consumption of 6.35 MWh. However, changes in occupancy patterns due to the introduction of hybrid working in 2021 prompted a re-evaluation (8).

To account for reduced occupancy, CO2 sensor-driven profiles were used to predict occupancy levels in each space and simulation timestep.

Converting the 2019 model into a 2022 model without ECMs (utilizing the 2022 weather file and occupancy profiles without flexible setpoints), the model predicted an energy consumption of approximately 7 MWh. Comparing this to the actual consumption (5.23 MWh) revealed a saving of 1.2 MWh or 17.1%. This saving was attributed to two factors: a 10.2% reduction due to a heating remote switch-off during public holidays, specifically Christmas time, and a 6.9% saving from the implementation of a smart thermostat and variable setpoints in meeting and training rooms. Figure 8 illustrates the heating energy use in MWh for Decembers (2019-2022) compared to simulation results.

Figure 5 – The heating energy use in MWh for Decembers (2019-2022) compared to simulation results.

6.0 Expansion to a Mixed-Use Building in Grenoble, France

The research scope expanded to include the World Trading Centre (WTC), a mixed-use building in Grenoble, France. In contrast to the Helix building in Glasgow, the WTC employs a Heat Pump (HP) for heating, utilizing hot water loops that feed Fan Coil Units (FCUs) and a mechanical ventilation system in common areas. Despite these variations, both buildings embraced the innovative approach of a variable setpoint and an HVAC system triggered by occupancy. Notably, this study focused on two specific floors (floors 5 & 8) within the WTC, chosen for the ongoing Research & Development (R&D) project, iBECOME (9).

These selected floors consist of offices and lecture rooms, providing an ideal testing ground for occupancy-triggered HVAC systems. The diverse patterns of room usage, varying across different spaces, days of the week, and throughout the calendar year, make these floors well-suited for assessing the effectiveness of the implemented systems.

Figure 6 – A picture of the WTC building (Available online at google maps (11))

In the WTC building, FCUs are connected to a Schneider Web-based Building Management System (BMS). This system allows adjustments to target temperatures for various rooms via server-less resources using API requests, facilitated by Microsoft Azure time-triggered functions (10).

It's important to note that, during the drafting of this paper, the Digital Twin of the WTC was still undergoing calibration. Consequently, the evaluation focused solely on real-life testing of the implemented control approach, involving occupancy-triggered heating and cooling, capturing occupant feedback, and observing the system's response.

The accompanying timeseries plot illustrates the indoor room temperature alongside the effective setpoint. The WTC system allows occupants to apply offsets to the

setpoint, termed the effective setpoint, as shown in Figures 10 and 11 below, plotted using IES-iSCAN Data Analysis Tool (11).

Figure 7 – Flexible setpoints in an office space in the WTC building (Grey), indoor temperature (Green) and the signal from the presence sensor which drives the changes in setpoint (Blue) in a moderately occupied day.

Figure 8 – Flexible setpoints in an office space in the WTC building (Grey), indoor temperature (Green) and the signal from the presence sensor which drives the changes in setpoint (Blue) in a mostly unoccupied day.

Note that Figure (10) represents a typical Thursday in winter 2023. The presence sensor data indicates that a significant portion of occupied hours reflects unused space. Consequently, the target temperature was slightly lowered to maximize potential energy savings. When the presence sensor detects occupancy, the target temperature can increase to 20 degrees Celsius, with a variability of \pm the offset controlled by occupants.

In contrast, Figure (11) shows the same plot the next day, a Friday, typically characterized by lower building activity. With this control strategy, the room temperature was maintained at 18 degrees Celsius to minimize the gap to the 20 degrees Celsius actual setpoint when someone enters the space. Applying uniform heating to the building on quiet days, similar to busy days, could overlook significant energy-saving opportunities, especially considering reduced internal gains in unoccupied spaces.

The unpredictability of occupant behaviours emphasizes the importance of avoiding a rigid heating schedule on quiet days, as it could result in a complete isolation for those spaces from the heating system, as it may compromise occupant comfort. Therefore, the implementation of live-data-driven control is a key when deploying such techniques.

7.0 Considerations of Comfort Issues

The comfort of occupants poses challenges in implementing solutions to buildings, aligning with the iBECOME project's goal of developing innovative energy-saving solutions without compromising indoor comfort (9).

The observed comfort issues in this study can be categorized into two groups: those related to the Helix building and those related to the WTC building.

7.1. *Comfort issues for the Helix building:*

- The radiator-based system includes a zone thermostat for regulating heating availability. However, there's a potential issue since the temperature sensor controlling the system's availability is positioned in the main office. Despite this, all meeting rooms have exposed walls, making them more vulnerable to lower temperatures than the rest of the office. If the outdoor temperature isn't sufficiently low, the internal gains in the main office may lead the zonal thermostat to turn off at times when heating is necessary in some meeting rooms.
- The occupants lack access to the TRV target temperature, resulting in situations where not all individuals can be satisfied, given that different occupants may have distinct preferences for room temperature based on their thermal comfort preferences.
- The system in the Helix building is a bit old and the TRV valves sometimes are hard for the IoT motor to move. This translates into the valve not being completely shut which might lead to missing the whole point of not heating unoccupied spaces, or stop the heating when reaching the desired temperature due to hardware. See figure 12 below:

Figure 9 – IoT-Controlled HVAC System Challenges: Aging TRV Valves Impacting Efficiency in Helix Building

- The IoT-operated system requires enhanced monitoring due to its reliance on devices like motors and sensors connected to the internet. In the event of a lost connection, the system defaults to the latest command sent to the devices, posing a potential risk to the building's temperature control, leading to either inadequate heating or overheating. Moreover, since many IoT devices operate on batteries, monitoring of parameters such as battery voltage for each device is crucial. This added responsibility places an extra burden on the building manager, highlighting the essential need for micro-level monitoring to ensure the system's optimal performance and prevent potential disruptions.
- There is a risk of poor air quality when there is reduced heating, leading to fewer expected window openings, which might result in a spike in CO₂ levels.

7.2. *Comfort issues for the WTC building:*

- Due to inadequate design or ineffective space partitioning, certain south-facing spaces experience a significant amount of solar gains during the summer. This can pose challenges for the Fan Coil Units (FCUs) in efficiently cooling down these areas during the cooling season, especially if they are not pre-cooled initially.
- The 2-degree temperature difference has been found to have distinct impacts on occupant behaviour, varying between summer and winter. In winter, individuals were observed to be generally happy with a temperature 2 degrees lower than the setpoint (20 degrees) when they first entered the space, and they were willing to compromise some comfort. However, in the summer, a 2-degree increase above the setpoint of 26 degrees, resulting in 28 degrees, was reported to the building manager as too hot.
- Some occupants have the habit of switching off the AC/Heating unit before they leave. This puts the FCU on manual mode and it can no longer be

controlled remotely, which means the control algorithm will not be able to reach the unit for preheating or precooling.

8.0 Conclusion and Recommendations:

In conclusion, this study addresses the pivotal question of optimizing heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems in infrequently occupied spaces, with a particular focus on meeting and training rooms. Utilizing a combination of digital-twin technology and real-world measurements, the research provides a thorough analysis. Through simulations and practical applications in both a Glasgow office building and the World Trading Centre (WTC) in Grenoble, France, the study demonstrates substantial energy savings, achieving a 17.1% reduction in heating energy consumption verified by real-world implementation. Additionally, the research explores and discusses the challenges associated with the IoT-based control of HVAC systems, underscoring the necessity of addressing complexities to strike a harmonious balance between energy efficiency and occupant comfort. These findings contribute valuable insights for building managers and policymakers, highlighting practical considerations essential for successful implementation in diverse environments.

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